

METHOD VALIDATION FOR THE DETERMINATION OF N-NITROSODIBUTYLAMINE (NDBA) IMPURITY FOR GABAPENTIN CAPSULES USING LIQUID CHROMATOGRAPHY-HIGH RESOLUTION MASS SPECTROMETRY (LC-HRMS)

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ABSTRACT

Nitrosamines impurities have strong carcinogenic potential which are making drug safety monitoring crucial. Recent detection of nitrosamines impurities in various drugs has led regulatory agencies to increase surveillance and almost all the regulatory bodies issue guidelines to control these impurities. Gabapentin, being one of the most widely prescribed drugs, has been one of the candidate for possible presence of nitrosamine impurities. In this article an analytical method developed to detect N-Nitrosodibutylamine (NDBA) in Gabapentin Capsules (100 mg, 300 mg, and 400 mg) using Liquid Chromatography-High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC-HRMS) has been validated as per the requirements of International Council for Harmonization (ICH) and United States Pharmacopeia (USP) guidelines. The LC-HRMS method was validated for its system suitability, specificity, system precision, method precision, quantification limits, and detection limits. System precision showed % RSD (n=6) of 5.0% with no blank interference, The method is specific for determination of NDBA Impurity as there was no interference from the blank and placebo at the retention time of NDBA impurity, while the system precision showed % RSD (n=6) of retention time of 0.7% and % RSD (n=6) of Area response was 5.0%. Method precision had % RSD (n=6) of 2.2%. The method achieved a limit of detection (LOD) of 0.05342 ng/mL (0.000742 ppm) and a limit of quantitation (LOQ) of 0.16188 ng/mL (0.002250 ppm). These results confirm the method's accuracy, sensitivity, and reliability for routine quality control analysis.

KEYWORDS: gabapentin; n-nitrosodibutylamine; LC-HRMS; analytical method validation; nitrosamine impurities; pharmaceutical quality control.

1. INTRODUCTION

Generics of NEURONTIN is Gabapentin which is a synthetic analog of gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)¹. This is primarily used for the treatment of neuropathic pain and epilepsy. Gabapentin acts by

modulating voltage-gated calcium channels and thus reducing excitatory neurotransmitter release.² The US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved Neurontin (gabapentin) in December 1993, and since its approval, it has been widely used due to its effectiveness and relatively favorable safety profile.³

U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) and European Medicines Agency (EMA) have emphasized the necessity of monitoring nitrosamine impurities in pharmaceutical formulations. US FDA comes up with updated guidance in 2024 “Control of Nitrosamine Impurities in Human Drugs”⁴ which revises the guidance of the same title issued in February 2021. One of the Nitrosamines, e.g. N-Nitrosodibutylamine (NDBA), are classified as probable human carcinogens based on their genotoxic potential. The presence of these impurities in drug products has posed significant health risks and thus necessitating stringent regulatory oversight.⁵

However, the detection and quantification of nitrosamines at trace levels require highly sensitive analytical techniques. US FDA, Health Canada has published several methodologies to detect and quantify different nitrosamines and Recommended Acceptable Intake Limits for Nitrosamine Drug Substance-Related Impurities (NDSRIs)⁹. Liquid Chromatography-High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC-HRMS) appeared to be preferred method due to its high specificity, sensitivity, and ability to accurately differentiate between structurally similar compounds. This article focuses on the validation of an LC-HRMS method for determining NDBA impurities in Gabapentin Capsules. The developed LC-HRMS method was validated following ICH guidelines⁶ and USP⁷ to ensure its compliance with regulatory standards. In this validation study established its system suitability, specificity, system precision, method precision, quantification limits, and detection limits⁸. Appropriately validated method provide assurance on product quality and avoid out of specification results due to analytical error.¹⁰⁻¹¹

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Chemicals and Reagents

For this method validation study high-purity reagents and pharmaceutical-grade materials were utilized to ensure the accuracy and reproducibility of the developed analytical method. NDBA standard (B. No. L47-076, expiry: 30-Apr-2021), with a purity of 99.96%, was obtained from a certified reference material supplier. LC-MS grade solvents, including formic acid, methanol, acetonitrile, and water, were sourced from Biosolve and were used to prepare mobile phases and sample solutions to minimize contamination.

2.2 Instrumentation

This method validation activities were performed using Dionex HPLC Ultimate 3000 system coupled with a Q Exactive Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer of Thermo-Fisher Scientific. The separation was achieved using column X Bridge C18 150mm x 4.6 mm 3.5 μ m (Make: Waters, Part No. 186003034), which ultimately provided required resolution and peak shape.

2.3 Chromatographic Conditions

An optimized HPLC method was developed to ensure precise separation and detection of the NDBA impurity. The developed gradient method consisted of Mobile Phase A: 0.1% formic acid in water (1.0mL Formic acid added to 1000mL of water and mixed well), Mobile Phase B: 0.1% formic acid in methanol (1.0mL Formic acid added to 1000mL Methanol and mixed well). Mobile phase flow rate was maintained at 0.6 mL/min, 5 μ L sample injection volume was used for adequate detection sensitivity. The column temperature was maintained at 40°C while sample temperature was maintained at 15°C. Needle was washed before and after each injection with 0.5% Formic Acid in Acetonitrile. Diluent and blank were prepared with a ratio of Formic Acid: Acetonitrile: Water (0.5:60:40) % v/v. Gradient Program maintained as (Table 1):

Table 1: Gradient Program for HPLC Separation.

Time (in mins)	Mobile Phase-A (in %)	Mobile Phase-B (in %)
0.0	40	60
5.0	40	60
7.0	30	70
10.0	20	80
11.0	10	90
13.0	10	90
14.0	40	60
15.0	40	60

2.4 Mass Spectrometer Conditions

Mass spectrometer condition was set as specified in Table: 2 with ion source setting positive and scan setting is specified in Table: 3. Detection was performed in positive ionization mode at an m/z value of 159.14919.

Table 2: Mass Spectrometer Setting.

Sheath Gas Flow Rate	60 arbitrary units
Aux Gas Flow Rate	15 arbitrary units
Sweep Gas Flow Rate	0 units
Spray Voltage	3.5 Kv
Capillary Temp.	250 °C
S-Lens	55 (applied to Q Exactive™)
Aux Gas Heater Temp.	450 °C

Table 3: Scan Setting.

Scan Type	SIM
Polarity	Positive
Scan Start -End (min)	6.9 to 15 min
m/z Isolated for PRM	159.14919
NCE	NA
Isolation Window	1.5 m/z
Micro scans	3
Resolution	70,000
AGC target	1e6
Maximum IT	100 ms

2.5 Preparation of Standard, Placebo and Sample Solutions

NDBA Standard Stock solution-1: (1mg/mL)

Accurately weigh and transfer 20mg of NDBA Standard into 20mL volumetric flask, add 10mL of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and dilute to volume with methanol and mix well.

NDBA Standard Stock solution-2: (0.01mg/mL)

Transfer 1mL of the above NDBA Standard Stock solution-1 to 100mL volumetric flask and dilute to volume with methanol and mix well.

NDBA Standard Stock solution-3: (100ng/mL)

Transfer 1mL of the above NDBA Standard Stock solution-2 to 100mL volumetric flask and dilute to volume with methanol and mix well.

Standard solution (0.53 ng/mL)

Transfer a 0.53mL aliquot volume of the NDBA Standard stock solution-3 into a 100 mL volumetric flask and dilute to volume with diluent and mix well.

Preparation of Placebo Solution

Weigh and transfer Placebo powder (approx. 145mg) equivalent to 720mg of Gabapentin into 20 mL GC vial, add 10mL of diluent and mix for a minute using a vortex mixer. Shake the sample for 40 minutes manually. After extraction, centrifuge the sample for 15 minutes at 4500 rpm. Filter the supernatant using a 0.2 μ m PVDF syringe filter, discard the first 1 mL of filtrate and transfer the filtered sample into an HPLC vial.

Preparation of Sample Solution: (72 mg/mL)

Weigh 20 Capsules and determine the average fill weight of Capsules. Weigh and transfer sample powder (approx. 865mg) equivalent to 720mg of Gabapentin into 20 mL GC vial, add 10mL of diluent and mix for a minute using a vortex mixer. Shake the sample for 40 minutes manually. After extraction, centrifuge the sample for 15 minutes at 4500 rpm. Filter the supernatant using a 0.2 μ m PVDF syringe filter, discard the first 1 mL of filtrate and transfer the filtered sample into an HPLC vial.

3. Method Validation

3.1 System Suitability

To check system suitability parameters, 3 injections of blank solution and then six injections of standard solution were considered. The % RSD (n = 6) of the NDBA peak areas from the first six injections of the standard solution were evaluated along with interference of blank from injection of blank. Results are tabulated in Table: 4 and the corresponding chromatogram of blank and reference standard are presented in Figure: 1 and 3 respectively.

Table 4: System Suitability Results.

Sr. No	Acceptance criteria	Results
1	The % RSD (n = 6) of the NDBA peak areas from the first six injections of the standard solution	5.0
2	The Blank interference from the injection of blank should	No interference observed

3.2 System Suitability

Specificity of the method has been validated by injecting Blank, Standard solution, Placebo Solution Sample solution and Spiked sample solution into the LC-HRMS system. The retention time (RT) of Blank, Standard solution, Placebo solution, Sample solution and Spiked sample solution were recorded in Table: 5.

Table 5: Outcome of Specificity Study.

Sample Name	Peak Name	RT (Minutes)
Blank	Blank	Not Detected
Standard Solution	NDBA	9.54
Placebo Solution	Not Applicable	Not Detected
As such sample	NDBA	9.55
Spiked sample	NDBA	9.54

3.3 System Precision

Prepared solution of Blank (3 Injections) and Standard solution (6 Injections) were injected into the LC-HRMS system. %RSD of Retention time and Area response for NDBA Impurity from standard solution (6 Injections) were calculated and tabulated in Table: 6 and related chromatogram of standard solution is presented in Figure: 3

Table 6: Results of System Precision

Injection No.	NDBA impurity	
	Retention Time (min)	Peak area
1	9.54	355460
2	9.63	347498
3	9.55	318975
4	9.71	337587
5	9.55	321711
6	9.54	315199
Mean	9.587	332738.333
% RSD	0.7	5.0

3.3 Method Precision

Gabapentin Sample solution contains no NDBA at quantitation limit thus In Method precision, a homogeneous sample of a single batch was prepared by spiking NDBA at working level concentration (0.53ng/mL) and this spiked solution was analyzed six times using LC-HRMS system. Outcome of method precision has been presented in Table: 7 and as such sample chromatogram is presented in Figure: 4.

Table 7: Outcome of Method Precision.

Sample No	NDBA (ppm)
1	0.0048
2	0.0049
3	0.0049
4	0.0046
5	0.0048
6	0.0048
% Mean	0.005
% RSD	2.2

3.3 Limit of detection and Limit of Quantitation

The sensitivity of the method was established through LOD and LOQ determinations. To check the method sensitivity NDBA Impurities solutions were prepared at LOD and LOQ Concentration and injected into LC-HRMS System and recorded the area responses to calculate the LOD and LOQ for NDBA peak area response. Elution of distinct visible peak for LOD level was check and % RSD of the area response obtained from 6 injections at LOQ level were calculated. Results of LOQ level precision and Signal / Noise Ration of LOQ & LOD are tabulated in Table: 8 & 9 respectively and the final LOQ & LOD level is tabulated in Table: 10.

Table 8: Precision at LOQ Level.

Sr. No	Area of NDBA Impurity
1	119600
2	112508
3	130173
4	109508
5	108735
6	116336
Average	116143.333
% RSD	6.9

Table 9: LOQ & LOD of the method.

NDBA Impurity	S/N Ratio	
NDBA	LOD	159
	LOQ	416

Table 10: Final Results of LOD and LOQ.

NDBA Impurity	LOD (in ng/mL)	LOD (in ppm)	LOQ (in ng/mL)	LOQ (in ppm)
N-Nitroso dibutyl amine (NDBA)	0.053420	0.000742	0.161880	0.002250

Figure 1: Chromatogram of Blank Solution.

Figure 2: Chromatogram of Placebo.

Figure 3: Chromatogram of Standard.

4. DISCUSSION

The developed method for the determination of N-Nitrosodibutylamine (NDBA), shown to be reliable throughout the analysis, as indicated by relative standard deviation (%RSD, n=6) of peak areas in system suitability analysis, which was 5.0%. No interference was also observed from the blank thus confirmed the

method's specificity. Moreover, blank and placebo interference studies showed no interfering peaks at the retention time of N-Nitrosodibutylamine (NDBA) this ensure accurate identification and quantification of impurity and confirm the specificity of the method.

The retention time (%RSD 0.7%, n=6) and area responses (%RSD 0.5%, n=6) was found to be consistent, demonstrating required system precision. Method precision was further confirmed by six independent sample preparations which yielded RSD of 2.2%, thus validating the method's reproducibility for NDBA determination.

The method's sensitivity was proven through the determination of the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ). The LOD was 0.05342 ng/mL (0.000742 ppm), confirming the ability to detect trace levels of NDBA. The LOQ was 0.16188 ng/mL (0.002250 ppm), ensuring reliable quantitation with acceptable precision and accuracy.

Figure 4: Chromatogram of Sample Solution.

5. CONCLUSION

The developed LC-HRMS method demonstrated high specificity, precision, and sensitivity for detecting N-Nitrosodibutylamine (NDBA) impurity in Gabapentin Capsules. The method met ICH and USP guidelines, with no interference from blank or placebo, confirming its selectivity.

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